

INTELLECTUAL AND IMMATERIAL BANK

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

BY WISE JESTER

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August 2021, Oslo, Norway

What is it?

The Intellectual and Immaterial Bank by Wise Jester is a blind, humor-based, algorithmically assisted network for intellectual inclusion and neurodiversity. IIB facilitates emergence of collaborations with shared visions, equipped with hybrid knowledge, imagination [and more] quantified, and improvisations by the users: for solving difficult problems.

Deployed?

YES. IIB online:

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

Visual explanation of IIB

USERS: persons with professional interests

all of them are on the same plane because each person is naturally different from another

IT IS THEM ALL, YOU, AND ME

Visual explanation of IIB

USERS: persons with professional interests

each person has an own bouquet of intellectual patterns to apply when contexts collide

Your strongest capacity for making change is having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.

While thinking, you are rather after imagination.
 You tend to react immediately to cognitive signals.
 You prefer working in independent genre.

**Complex Systems, Hybrid Innovation, Entrepreneurship,
 Social Work, Music**

preferred comfort zones
 instant-th. triggers
 deep-th. triggers
 capacities for transformation

- Low-pressure contexts
- Contexts with high uncertainty
- Collectivistic environments
- High-pressure contexts
- Independent genre
- Social signals
- Cognitive signals
- Emotional signals
- Knowledge
- Focused aim
- Solidarity with others
- Imagination
- Coming up with alternatives
- Faster taking the new into practice
- Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
- Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
- Breaking old things down faster
- Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

how you thought things to take course

BOOM!

he-he,
 new data

What would you do?

How?

Why?

This is you from any of the above

and you "look" for others
...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally assisted...

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

Pitched:

I am a dreamer and doer who wants to build intelligence-intensive mechatronic solutions of tomorrow.

among all who are available for you to be discovered

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics.**
 Pitched: I am crazy about math and physics, because we can make even more new solutions if we better understand Mother Nature!

to compile a collaboration with you

Username: sjaqpqkgjagd652o1hwekhsjgkah82o2tyuq2jgdqhgwhfqkjh
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 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics.**
 Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: qjgksjdjahgdw82632jgahfwhqjt2i1gsgdj1tidbj2tksvghj187ejs
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **breaking old things down faster.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**
 Pitched: Robots are my everything. I worked in industrial robotics, and now I want to build a humanoid of my own.

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

This is you from any of the above

and you "look" for others
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INTRODUCE YOURSELF

with a shared dream or vision

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INTRODUCE YOURSELF

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Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

with hybrid knowledge

Username: qjgksjdjahgdw82632jgahfwhqjt2i1gsgdj1tidbj2tksvghj187ejs

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INTRODUCE YOURSELF

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

Why is humor an innovative solution here?

Humor is a special area of cognitive science. Humor is about **colliding situations** that relate. Brain “solves” a joke and **rewards itself** with a smile or laugh, which cannot be faked. Humor is based on **re-composition of what people know and can synthesize**, when they “crack” the code of a joke by getting it. Considering that jokes demonstrate a rich **diversity**, individual appreciation of humor is naturally **unique**. To collaborate is a process and a skill, exploring a balance between **certainty and uncertainty**, compatibility and challenge. **Humor code-cracking qualities** give a great clue about it!

Jim Morrison, The Doors:

“I've noticed that when people are joking, they're usually dead serious, and when they're serious, they're usually pretty funny.”

Your capacities

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**

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You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

- preferred comfort zones
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- capacities for transformation
 - Faster taking the new into practice
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
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 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

Needs of your collaboration

Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck.**

Your collaboration may experience **ignoring uniqueness.**
Your collaboration might be overlooking **how others feel.**
Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by expecting **individual initiative.**

- disruption of comfort
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How others feel
 - Siloed thinking
 - Being too dispersed
- Intellectual depth
 - Ignoring uniqueness
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
- needs in transformation
 - Fear of deviation
 - Seeing the big picture
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the members
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

What can the humor module of IIB do?

In IIB, humor appreciation provides data generation, computed to show you your own unique way of thinking when contexts collide. Properly argued and anchored in Humor Science, the module shows you your instinctive (unconscious, autopilot) thinking and deeper (conscious aware) thinking, beautifully theorized by Daniel Kahneman, who got a Nobel prize in behavioral economics for that. The theory was further developed by a humor scientist Larry Ventis, and his peers in Cognitive Science, Linguistics, Psychology, Behaviorism, and more. Also, that theory was accurately applied by Jon Ivar Johansen to explore change processes in organizations, starting from individuals. Compiled in a unique way with practice, the elements of the accumulated knowledge emerged into a synthesized, relationship-intensive module in IIB, full of mathematical calculations, created and applied by the founder of Wise Jester with background in science and a bunch of other knowledge & practice areas. Mathematically and computationally, IIB considers the tendency of human mind to equilibrium and, also, values its natural “edge of chaos”, including such features as imagination and spontaneity.

A permanent link to a document with some relevant science extracts:
<https://zenodo.org/record/4724974>

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I wonder, where did people cough before theater was invented?

26/36

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

[BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION](#)

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

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Login

In 1855, Alexander ascended the royal throne. But the login was already taken, and he had to become Alexander II.

0 1 2 3 4 5

19/36

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Workaholic Anton calls his former employers when drunk.

10/36

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[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

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Visual explanation of IIB

USERS: collaborations of independent professionals

your collaboration acts as a bouquet of needs when contexts collide, looking for hybrid knowledge, and the vision shared

- | | |
|-------------------------|---|
| disruption of comfort | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Pressuring the members ■ Demanding clarity and plan ■ Expecting individual initiative ■ Slowing down for well-ordered actions ■ Accountability and transparency |
| tendency to ignore | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The socially accepted ■ Facts and numbers ■ How others feel ■ Siloed thinking ■ Being too dispersed ■ Ignoring uniqueness ■ Being too down-to-earth |
| Intellectual depth | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Structures and processes that are stuck ■ Fear of deviation ■ Seeing the big picture ■ Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas ■ Degree of inner passion of the members ■ Potential for synergic collaboration |
| needs in transformation | |

how you as a group think when you...

BOOM!

have a date with new data

How do you look?

Your collaboration is not pictured as a trendy name, big tokens, or well-dressed C[X]Os with wide white smiles – because you should not be marginalizing yourself from evolution.

Needs of your collaboration

IIB will be honest with you, but nobody else will see that this is you!

Because IIB is blind like a bat, and he makes all his users blind too – to see further and better.

Your collaboration may have a challenge with fear of deviation.

Your collaboration may experience ignoring uniqueness.

Your collaboration might be overlooking how others feel.

Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by expecting individual initiative.

you as a collaboration act like an attractor,
DEMAND for SUPPLY

+

-

Needs of my collaboration

and you "look" for others
 ...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally
 assisted...

Your collaboration may have a challenge with structures and processes that are stuck.
 Your collaboration may experience being too dispersed.
 Your collaboration might be overlooking the socially accepted.
 Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by pressuring the members.

Pitched:

Our team is looking for a bright developer who understands the social complexity around emerging technologies and can work fast.

Are you aware of Physics? You are a "plus".

...among 'em all

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: jwgejay2731kjqhwmai2u01lkqajy2g1jhf62reamo03egh120

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is faster taking the new into practice.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in collectivistic environments.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for solidarity with others.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: coding, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: statistics, physics, engineering.

Pitched: I am a Java developer, and I am available to become a part of a new environment. I love travelling too.

to strengthen up the collaboration

Username: sjghwja721klwjka89q2kajwhdjba827jhwekq3ryhjfqh62jq2g

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in high-pressure contexts.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for imagination.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: xr, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, entrepreneurship, engineering.

Pitched: I am developing a new type of digital wallets. I am looking for collaborations that develop respective user applications.

with a shared dream or vision

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjksqqlqk

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is breaking old things down faster.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in contexts with high uncertainty.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for focused aim.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: coding, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, math, engineering.

Pitched: My dream is to create machines that talk!

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

And they are "minuses".

you as a collaboration act like an attractor,
DEMAND for SUPPLY

+

-

Needs of my collaboration

and you "look" for others
 ...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally
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Your collaboration may have a challenge with structures and processes that are stuck.
 Your collaboration may experience being too dispersed.
 Your collaboration might be overlooking the socially accepted.
 Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by pressuring the members.

Pitched:

Our team is looking for a bright developer who understands the social complexity around emerging technologies and can work fast.

...you are a "plus" ...

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 Pitched: I am developing a new type of digital wallets. I am looking for collaborations that develop respective user applications.

with hybrid knowledge

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 Pitched: My dream is to create machines that talk!

...and they are "minuses" ...

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

IIB is a fair game. Not only collaborations can look for people, but people can look for collaborations.
SYMMETRY! Because why not?

...and they are “plusses”...

Your strongest capacity for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **cognitive signals.**
 You prefer working in **independent genre.**
Pitched:
 I am a maker of IIB, and I am looking for more bright and dedicated people to join me in this world

...you are a “minus” ...

Collaboration name: The Lorenz family

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **obvious needs in new, unknown ideas.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **demanding clarity and plan.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **robotics, math, entrepreneurship.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **arts, hybrid innovation.**
Pitched: We are programmers who can simulate chaos for you or an egde of it. Tokenized. And we are looking for a lawyer.

Collaboration name: Experiment Stitch

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **fear of deviation.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **expecting individual initiative.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **robotics, math, entrepreneurship.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **arts, hybrid innovation.**
Pitched: Mechatronic animation for visualizations of dreams.

Collaboration name: Wonders of Emergence

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **obvious needs in new, unknown ideas.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **expecting individual initiative.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **robotics, math, entrepreneurship.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **arts, hybrid innovation.**
Pitched: 011235813213455891442333776109871597...

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from August 12, 2021]

Wise Jester

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

News about IIB

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Login

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

Physics Engineering Statistics Math XR Robotics Coding Regulation
Economics Gaming Entrepreneurship User experience Social work Writing
Music Complex systems Hybrid innovation Communication Arts Sports
Medicine Blockchain Environment Audiovisual works Design Art

DONE!

these can always be enriched

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BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

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USERS: collaborations of independent professionals

For every request, IIB compiles at least 3 out of 5 knowledge areas, with the 1st area in the request as obligatory, plus shows unique options, out of the request, from the receivers' choices of knowledge areas – for every computationally assisted connection in deeper and instant thinking, computed from individual humor appreciation when contexts collide.

combinations of domain knowledge into hybrid, approved individually by selection and vision-based, informed choice making, in no social pressure on the individuals, acting in harmonious collaborations, compiled in intellectual compatibility and challenge

emergence of new industries
 from more projects solving difficult problems
 minimizing the gap between conventional industries and emerging technologies
 with intellectual inclusion and neurodiversity

having fun

+ and/or any of your friends and colleagues by invitation

Communication on IIB

Me contacting individuals [independent professionals]:

- On my behalf _____
- On behalf of my collaboration _____

Me contacting collaborations

Me being contacted:

- By other individuals [independent professionals]
- By collaborations

Conversations in my collaborations

My everybody

What can that give to you? That is the fun part: surprises.

But! You must be a person of integrity and respect other people. Don't steal, don't cheat. Behave decent.

I regularly update the General Instruction and News.

TEAM Wise Jester

The founder of Wise Jester, born 2019, **Anna Zaytseva**, born 1987, has been working on the IIB concept for 11 years. I received a PhD in **Management of Information Systems** for that purpose and worked with content development at an innovation-support center for social welfare solutions in South Norway. I am building IIB as a **Complex System**. I have a certificate from the **Complex Systems Summer School** at the Santa Fe Institute, a master's degree in **International and European Relations** and an honors specialist degree in **Jurisprudence**. I am the brain and engine of the IIB development.

The web developer **Alexey Egoshin** holds a PhD in **Mathematical Modelling**, a patent in **chaos simulation**, more than 12 years of experience in **web engineering**, and a portfolio of **collaborative projects** with companies from the USA, Europe, Canada and Israel. The projects include a web platform for optimizing recruitment and branding, game strategies, and a web platform for trading on financial markets. He has been working with me on IIB until now from September 2020.

The advisor **Massimo Stella** holds a PhD in **Complex Systems Simulations** and post-doc experience in **Data Science**. He is a founder of **Complex Science Consulting**, and a lecturer at the University of Exeter. Massimo does **psycholinguistics** and cognitive experiments in **change of mindsets** when people transfer from one knowledge area to another by **collaboration** or **individual choice making**. With Massimo, we did a psycholinguistic experiment and pitched it at TEDx Arendal, exhibition.

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

wisejester@intellectualandimmaterialbank.com

**LOOKING FOR INVESTORS
AND CO-FOUNDERS**

*Cordially,
Anna A. Zaytseva,*

Founder of Wise Jester AS